

Precision object tracking in a drone system

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Abstract—This paper discusses the possibility of implementing through various algorithms for the Detection and tracking of relatively moving objects like tennis balls with observed movement with reference to the Drone (Quadcopter and fixed-wing) with an installed camera system (reference frame). Contrary to the past approaches of the more commonly used sensor-based solutions, our studies are dedicated to devising lighter and more cost-effective systems which are expected to break up the market with the latest assistive technology products. The algorithms to be implemented within the scope of this have to be rigorously equipped and checked for real-time speed, efficiency, and accuracy before being put into use and considering the various capabilities of unmanned aerial vehicles this is done based on the following setups.

The experimental setup for the virtue of this have to include drones equipped with advanced imaging technology that have a combination of existing and theorized algorithms in addition to hardware setup instruments for generating dynamic object trajectories and then comparing the simulated result against those obtained from professional, high-quality footage. Besides these evaluation points, we also examine the flexibility of the tools in the real world. With the validation of the virtual work through algorithms being used in utilization bases by subjecting prototype drones to undergo the following modes based on Mavlink communication between Fcc and processor board to validate real-time processing and command by controller integration and change based on dynamics and control. Not only to show the result correlation between the simulated and practical systems but also to show the use case.

I. INTRODUCTION

Probably the most vital part of the research of our team concerns the designing of the drone control system that puts in the application of advanced computer vision techniques from the beginning. This proposal was suggested to be an agile solution that would enable the effective execution of precise manoeuvres with an objective of performing detection, tracking, and surveillance tasks in better ways. A major differentiating factor between our custom-built drone system and the off-the-shelf ones, which usually have software and hardware customization limitations, will be the ability to adopt and implement as many customized algorithms as needed according to the unique requirements of our computer vision tasks. Software was the main external tool used by us. We

elaborated thoroughly on an algorithm package for object visualization and monitoring. These algorithms make use of the latest technologies and artificial intelligence that allow the drone to track moving things with very high precision without being reminded. Data transmission in real time is one of the essential iterations of the software phase especially in the context of the monitoring and tracking tasks.

Only the set of the toughest tests was accepted for the verification of the reliability of the drone control system in different circumstances. This step consisted of the system's testing in a controlled environment where the program would be used, and the final process, field trials, where the drones were in charge of tracking actual moving objects, such as tennis balls. It was also important to evaluate the landing system's tracking precision along with its stability, manoeuvrability, and energy consumption, to confirm its feasibility for usage in real-life conditions over a long period of time.

With the virtue of making the drone control system from zero point, we have constructed an unassailable base to incorporate sophisticated computer vision classes into drone technology. This brings up the issue of regularly updating and enhancing the system's ability to track objects and moderate surveillance, not only. The increase in these aspects broadens the very range of the research and development works in the sphere of autonomous drones

II. RELATED WORKS

Following the invention of drones, a multitude of research endeavours have been undertaken to explore their applications across various domains. In 2017,[5] did a deep dive into the literature on the deep learning techniques applied to UAVs. These techniques are being utilized by deep learning algorithms for drones so that they can be made to classify scenes, localize objects and control movements towards the target. Planning and environment monitoring are also made better by the use of these algorithms.

In their study in 2015 on object detection by deep learning techniques, [7] gives a new descriptive of convolutional

MultiBoxes operating at different scales, called the multi-scale convolutional MultiBox method. This greatly improves detection accuracy and efficiency as compared to previous methods. A trademark is its highest by the fact that it uses a single model to achieve an mAP of 0.5 and the mAP after an ensemble has been trained is 0.52 on the ILSVRC 2014 dataset - this is the hardest dataset available. The MSC-MultiBox system evolves the art well by achieving the feat of having deep learning take care of the object proposal generation. This finally serves as the method of the job of recognizing objects from sensors is reduced. This grows being especially crucial for the UAV-based object detection algorithms which create a scalable and high-quality solution that does not handicap the performance due to the computational demands.

[8] on UAV empowers remote sensing technology across diverse regions like agriculture, forestry as well as mining. This essay reveals the standout human-eye resolution and flexible field of data acquisition of UAVs and shows that they are versatile tools for surveys. The authors target a thorough investigation of most of the data processing and analysis procedures with a UAV that accompanies the high-resolution imagery and the fusion of image data from multiple sensors. This examination then proceeds to demonstrate the use of UAVs, from land-cover classification to change detection, in which they are facilitating diversification of global missions; giving in situ awareness turnout is excellent. This roadmap is informative of the current uses and exactly points the future research direction, the writers thereby stress the giant potential and changeability of UAVs in remote sensing.

III. BACKGROUND

A. AI evolution in drones

Previously, drones with object detection, tracking, and mapping capabilities had to be equipped with a wide range of sensors, from such as thermal imaging for temperature measures, LiDAR for distance and depth mapping, ultrasound sensors for proximity detection, GPS for precise location tracking. This multisensor approach served very useful in accumulating environmental data from different dimensions which in turn ensured the object detection and tracking had been done robustly. Nonetheless, the emergence of sophisticated deep learning techniques allowed us to potentially double, and in some cases greatly increase, the abilities of our camera synthetic systems. Through using the CNNs (convolutional neural networks), we were able to develop a camera that interpreted visual data in a complex manner and analysed it more efficiently. These advancements have considerably reduced the need for activating a broad range of its sensors like infrared, LiDAR, ultrasonic and GPS by merging all the sensor's usage into one where drones can improve their visual capability and which helps to reduce hardware requirements by doing away with most sensors, thus making it perform more efficiently in the task it was designed to do.

B. Object detection and Communication

The protocol for this is run through communication between an onboard processing that helps provide the data in order for correction in flight attitude and the FCC that is tasked with the adjustment of the flight attitude based on the correction to the roll, pitch and yaw instruction governed by look ahead points and by utilization of the dynamics. The detection is based on the result set of either state flow or the detected coordinate position being feedback to the roll, yaw, and pitch connections in order to compensate for the difference in relative coordinate position. The interpretation of this is done by the usage of the processor module which communicates command messages with respect to the status messages which provide information about the flight status with the system under consideration needing to manipulate the reward out system status(such as mode, flight speed), Global position(altitude, latitude and longitude), the corrections set are based on the command messages that help set of maneuverability. [2]

Configuration of these message sets are based on usage of open source language python through Pymavlink library [3] in addition to the UAV blockset in conjunction with the computer vision blockset and the hardware support package of raspberry pi helps add the required interpretation data using Simulink. with the Mavlink commands being used here are EXTEND-SYS-STATE (ID 245) which allows presenting and or using the flight state values if the drone alongside MAV-FRAME-BODY (ID; 8) that allows control of the movement of the vehicle based on its position.

C. Way-point and object following

By the use of GCS the various waypoints can be added with mission modes such as land, take off, and loiter amongst others these help gain an aspect of semi-autonomy based on the points being fed in and dynamics compensation in order to reach said points the validation of which is based on GPS. The Data of the coordinate change based on the waypoint will be shown in the GCS [4].In terms of an object following one can observe that it is based on the coordinate determination in real-time with some systems using a predictive model to determine the path, this is a high fps process with the camera as sensor and if that's not used uses lidar.

IV. METHODOLOGY

A. Object motion tracking system

The framework is utilized for real-time discovery and tracking of flying objects utilizing a combination of OpenCV for image pre-processing, YOLOV8(You As it were See Once) for object detection and ByteTrack for protest following. It is outlined to address the challenges of precision of the framework in dynamic environments, centering on scenarios where objects showcase rapid development, shifting scales, work against complex backgrounds

1) *Preparing Dataset:* The dataset utilized for show training plays a pivotal part in the precision and strength of the model in diverse imperatives. The show is prepared on a

dataset of various sorts of UAVs in differing natural conditions and object configurations.

2) *Image Preprocessing using OpenCV*: Image preprocessing is done using OpenCV, a library that is widely used for different tasks in computer vision, before object detection. There are noise reduction, colour adjustment and other image processing techniques that are employed at this step to make the detection algorithm well-suited for operation. The preprocessing makes sure that the data input to the YOLOV8 model, be it image or video, is of top-notch quality to yield higher detection accuracy.

3) *Object detection using YOLOV8*: The algorithm is YOLOv8, an advanced and notable method in a single deep-learning architecture. It has proven to be outstanding in speed and accuracy in the detection of objects. This model is trained with data already prepared so it is able to determine the position of the tennis ball with high precision. Fine-tuning refers to matching the model's parameters to the ball as well. This way there will be a better place for it in the model to observe the flying object in a better way.

4) *Object tracking using ByteTrack*: Now that an object has been spotted, ByteTrack are used for detecting object tracking. Hereinafter, we shall show how this algorithm is particularly powerful in tracking fast-movement objects while they suddenly become segmented on another frame or occluder due to busy backgrounds.

5) *Coordinate Calculation*: The system obtains the 2D coordinates of the target object represented within the image frame having via the bounding box produced by YOLOv8. In order to get the object to the 3D area by using 2D information known, the z-axis is approved taking the camera focus known length. The triangulation in addition to the calibration of the camera provides the ability for the depth perception of the distance between the object and the photo camera. Hence, the system will be more effective when working with objects whose detection is based on the realistic position and curve.

B. Integration with drone system

1) *understanding the flight dynamics*: This is based on the configuration of the drone selected both a quadcopter as well as a fixed-wing with VTOL capabilities have been seen to satisfy the Use of precision motion tracking and its use as an input set for movement. The determination and understanding of this helps in creating the guidance logic and the dynamics in order to perform tasks such as tracking, following and the other task sets, taking the quadcopter in use for this we can understand the working based on the dynamics set which in turn helps get the mathematical model for the simulation set as well as determination of the value sets such as pitch change for the output/command interpretation of the Fcc

The quadcopter, possessing 6 degrees of freedom (6-DOF) and being under-actuated, is characterized by its four propellers positioned orthogonally to control vehicle balance and motion through differential propeller speed and direction. The dynamics of the quadcopter are described using the Newton-Euler translational and rotational dynamics formulation.

Given the quadcopter dynamics, where x, y, z are positions in the x, y, z axis, and $\dot{x}, \dot{y}, \dot{z}$ are the angular velocities. The angles ϕ, θ, ψ represent roll, pitch, and yaw respectively, and $\dot{\phi}, \dot{\theta}, \dot{\psi}$ are the speeds of roll, pitch, and yaw respectively.

$$\ddot{x} = \frac{1}{m} ((\sin \psi \sin \phi - \cos \psi \sin \theta \sin \phi)u_1 - A_x \dot{x}) \quad (1)$$

$$\ddot{y} = \frac{1}{m} ((\sin \psi \sin \phi - \cos \psi \sin \theta \sin \phi)u_1 - A_x \dot{y}) \quad (2)$$

$$\ddot{z} = \frac{1}{m} ((\cos \psi \sin \phi - \sin \psi \cos \phi \sin \theta)u_1 - A_y \dot{z}) \quad (3)$$

$$\ddot{z} = g - \frac{1}{m} (\cos \psi \cos \phi u_1 - A_z \dot{z}) \quad (4)$$

$$\ddot{\phi} = \left(\frac{I_{yy} - I_{zz}}{I_{xx}} \right) \dot{\psi} \dot{\theta} + \left(\frac{J_r \omega_r}{I_{xx}} \right) \dot{\theta} + \frac{l}{I_{xx}} U_2 - \left(\frac{A_\phi \dot{\phi}}{I_{xx}} \right) \quad (5)$$

$$\ddot{\theta} = \left(\frac{I_{zz} - I_{xx}}{I_{yy}} \right) \dot{\psi} \dot{\phi} + \left(\frac{J_r \omega_r}{I_{yy}} \right) \dot{\phi} + \frac{l}{I_{yy}} U_3 - \left(\frac{A_\theta \dot{\theta}}{I_{yy}} \right) \quad (6)$$

$$\ddot{\psi} = \left(\frac{I_{xx} - I_{yy}}{I_{zz}} \right) \dot{\theta} \dot{\phi} + \frac{l}{I_{zz}} U_4 - \left(\frac{A_\psi \dot{\psi}}{I_{zz}} \right) \quad (7)$$

Where:

- u_1 is the total thrust from the 4 rotors,
- U_2, U_3, U_4 are the moments for pitch, roll, and yaw respectively,
- I_{xx}, I_{yy}, I_{zz} are the moments of inertia about the x, y, z axes respectively,
- J_r is the rotor inertia, and ω_r is the rotor angular velocity,
- A_ϕ, A_θ, A_ψ are the aerodynamic damping coefficients for roll, pitch, and yaw,
- l is the arm length from the quadcopter's centre to the propeller.

2) *In-situ testing*: This starts with testing of the ground set up by usage initially of the ROs set up alongside the processor board in order to see the usage of the initial algorithm and its use in controlling the movement of the servomotors in order to move based on the camera's input with the movement such that it compensates for the difference of the different coordinate points to make the x and y coordinates as 0. This is done using the computer vision blocks of Simulink as well as the different hardware support packages. This can be seen by virtue of the Image in fig.3.

In addition, the testing of this is subjected to the utilization of a virtual digital twin added into a Simmultibody based on the model of the drone to be flown digital twin can be seen in Fig.2 with the system connections being shown in Fig.1. . This helps scope out as well as virtually test the iteration of the flight based on the parameters in order to check out the utilization of the dynamics and the change in response based on the input relation of the joint sets.

Fig. 1. Simulink QuadCopter MBSE

Fig. 2. Simulink QuadCopter Visualaization

Fig. 3. Hardware in a loop test with Openvc

3) *Integration of hardware:* Now the further process is done by the usage of the Pixhawk fcc alongside the processor board that is in use the board as input by virtue of the serial communication set or ROS alongside Mavlink the commands will be interpreted and sent in terms of position, velocity, attitude this will be interpreted and the control authority of the control systems which in there's of the quadcopter will be based on the torque and rpm of each motor and for the VTOL fixed wing will be based on the control surfaces will help provide the motion. the determination of which will be done by virtue of usage of the system in a model-based system environment for testing of dynamics and subsequent prototyping. The architecture of this can be seen using Fig.4. Validation of the

Fig. 4. Arcitecture

Fig. 5. Hardware

way point-based movement data by replication of the simulink scenario by utilization of mode switch and the position of the object in order to get the deviation of the recorded data to the virtually tested data. This is to determine the utilization of waypoint-based movement (using a system similar to Fig.5) vs the computer vision-based movement of the body based on the usage of waypoint based on known coordinates based on interpretation based on computer vision data.

4) *Improvement of response:* Improvements in this system are by usage of PID in order to help with delay as well as the

Fig. 6. Way point based testing

control system lags [6] and its utilization as well as tuning can be seen by using fig.6 and fig.7. This is used in all the stages with Kalman filters for the input as well as for the controller outputs. In addition, the feedback system will help identify the difference in the position of the drone as well as the tracked object. This is tested out based on the command module in Simulink that is trained based on the manual switch based on waypoint tracking, this is then embedded into the Mavlink code in order to provide status correction to the drone by substitution of the roll, pitch or yaw control with the controller based equation of the movement based on the interpretation of the coordinate by the computer vision set up. Improvements

Fig. 7. PID Usage

of the system based on the tested flight, have to be done keeping limit cases with respect to the attitude of the drone, and a fixed altitude range in order to avoid over-exhausting the flight or going over the constraints of the flight for example unrecoverable stall due to the angle of attack range reaching stall angle of attack.

Fig. 8. PID control Tuning

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Object Detection and Tracking

In real-time applications, the model detects objects with good precision, but it might need improvements. The table

Images	Detection	Confidences	TP	FP	Precision	Recall
1	A	88	0	1	0.5	0.1333
1	B	70	1	0	0.3	0.2
2	C	80	0	1	0.3333	0.1333
3	D	71	0	1	0.2222	0.1333
3	E	54	1	0	0.3846	0.3333
3	F	74	0	1	0.25	0.1333
4	G	18	1	0	0.3043	0.4666
4	H	67	0	1	0.2727	0.2

TABLE I
PERFORMANCE OF YOLOV8

shows test values for the YOLOv8 model, developed on a set of pictures of tennis balls. Precisions and recalls are calculated to score and measure the correctness and completeness of the findings. The direct definition of precision is its capability to predict the samples correctly while recall is the capability of the model to classify all the samples of a particular class. For example, anomaly detection as 'A' in Image 1 was credible but brought about FPs (false positive), thus reducing precision in addition to time consumption. On the contrary, the predicated output 'G' in Image 4, despite its lower confidence score, had a higher recall which amounts to correct identifications compromising a large percentage of the class. This is fundamental for the purpose of vertical tuning of YOLOv8, that is, balancing between detecting the most relevant objects as possible (high recall) and maintaining all the detections to be correct (high precision).

Fig. 9. X-Y-Z coordinates of the ball

The above figure demonstrates the detection of a ball and calculating its position in a 3D space. The system has identified key points on the ball's surface and computed the 3D coordinates, which are displayed.

B. Test of Drone path

Given the fact that the utilization of the code will be for the movement of the drone based on the relative position of the object and the attitude of the drone in the condition of detection, it is important to validate the path taken based on the validation of change in waypoint coordinates based on the position and coordinates of the object. This is done for

validation of the controller logic as well as the utilization and deviation in a drone when the object is tracked.

1) *Based on simulation: change in way points:* Given that The setup was created on Simulink in order to determine the dynamics relationship based on waypoint-based movement by utilization of a switch with different waypoint input we can observe the change in the path based on the waypoint that is at a region above the current waypoint, this is done in an attempt to replicate real-life intercept and tracking based objective. The observed pattern of flight alongside dampening can be observed with bases of validation for the physical model. An observable Switch can be seen while using Fig. 9 and Fig. 10 . But from previous research, it is known and observed in this too due to the dampening as well as environmental constraints there is a deviation in accuracy.

Fig. 10. Waypoint based movement

Fig. 11. Waypoint-based movement After detection coordinates

2) *Based on validation of simulation with test:* This formed the basis of understanding the deviation of the Simulated data from the tested-out data. This is done by comparing the plotted

values of the simulated data and the plotted out flight data based on flight here we can see observable deviation not only in the tuning data of the PID (seen in Fig 11) but also in the time period and position change based on the observation of an object (in the real world) vs way point switch in the simulation. Showing a lag time in the real-world condition is done by the virtue of replication of simulation by the placement of a position of the object relative to the simulated coordinates.

Controller Parameters		
	Tuned	Block
P	1004.993	6
I	5100.5079	0
D	-20.8437	1.5
N	28.275	10

Performance and Robustness		
	Tuned	Block
Rise time	0.078 seconds	0.962 seconds
Settling time	0.587 seconds	1.79 seconds
Overshoot	10.2 %	0 %
Peak	1.1	0.056
Gain margin	22.9 dB @ 121 rad/s	64.6 dB @ 274 rad/s
Phase margin	77.4 deg @ 16.7 rad/s	Inf deg @ NaN rad/s
Closed-loop stability	Stable	Stable

Fig. 12. Final Controller parameters used during linearization

3) *Realtime testing: response:* This is the final result set that shows the response time relative to the observation of the object as well as the positional accuracy based on the coded movement and Frame rate per second. This is observational based on flight. The linearization is based on the simulated [] real-time values and can be seen in fig.11.

VI. FUTURE WORK

Our future plan for the popularization of our research includes an element of immediate model training where by the dataset of minimum quantity plays a crucial role. The system starts with a data gathering basin of who's the onboard camera. The machine learning techniques used in the surveillance system are such that if the object to be detected is not from the group of objects which are previously known to the system then the system will not directly proceed to detection instead it will first enter into a learner stage. The procedure uses a host of image augmentation tools to produce a dataset with much that the limited data has to offer, ultimately allowing the model to learn from the few instances. After this, the model is trained by the dataset that is augmented until it attains an accuracy of 0.6 or higher. Now, only when the limit is exceeded will the model become confident enough to be

used for detection tasks, and its integration into the drone's control system will follow. The model used for this innovative

Fig. 13. Real-time model training and Deployment in Drone System

method features AI agility which allows for updating as well as learning in an almost real-time manner; which is much different to the traditional approach requires large data and time for it to be trained. Through the decreased requirement of hefty data files, this system guarantees high responsiveness and low adaptability to new objects or environments which, in turn, constitutes an important step to complete the usage of drone systems which possess self-learning and autonomy capabilities and operate in the fast-changing and unpredictable settings. With this approach, the time required would be reduced to the minimum as the cost of computation and data storage would be also reduced regularly, thereby increasing the effectiveness and viability of drone operations in various applications.

VII. CONCLUSION

our study demonstrates the potential of combining advanced computer vision techniques with drone technology to create versatile, efficient, and cost-effective solutions for object detection and tracking. This research not only showcases the practical application of these technologies but also sets the stage for future innovations in the field of autonomous drones, promising significant impacts on various sectors including surveillance, search and rescue operations, and environmental monitoring. Observable in the confines of this study is also the deviation of path compared to the waypoint simulation, the accuracy percentage of detection with a precision of .5 max percentage as well as lag based on the pid tuning and detection of the ball. Thus helping establish the need for future work as well as a better fps setup with a tuned control system for the studied utilization of the concept.

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